

Catalytic Activity of Hydrous Zirconium Oxide

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Hydrous oxide ZrO_2 is found to be a very potential catalyst towards the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide. The order of decomposition rises from one to two on increasing the dilution of the peroxide solution. The samples of hydrous oxide ZrO_2 , precipitated under different conditions, are found to differ considerably in their catalytic activity. The reactions are found to involve fairly low values of the energy of activation.

Ghosh and co-workers¹ have extensively investigated the hydrous oxides of several metals, such as, Ni(II), Fe(III), etc., for their various physical and chemical properties. Gyani and Nabe² have observed that hydrous ceric oxide is a fairly potent catalyst towards the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide. The author³ has observed that the catalytic activity of hydrous oxide ZrO_2 is greatly modified on irradiation with ultrasonic waves. During the course of present investigation it has been found that hydrous oxide ZrO_2 , precipitated under different conditions, behaves differently towards the catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide.

EXPERIMENTAL

Three different samples A, B and C of hydrous oxide ZrO_2 were precipitated by adding 10% deficient, equivalent, and 10% excess quantities, respectively, of 0.5882M solution of sodium hydroxide to a fixed volume of an aqueous 0.5876M solution of zirconium nitrate. The precipitates were thoroughly washed with distilled water, estimated, and suspended in re-distilled CO_2 -free water. These suspensions were separately used to catalyse the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide solutions of varying concentrations in a buffered medium (acetate buffer; pH 6.0). The kinetic experiments were carried out in opaque Jena glass bottles kept at desired temperature in a thermostatic water bath. All the chemicals used were of purest available variety.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

While following the kinetics of the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide solutions in the concentration range 0.008–0.10N, catalysed in presence of the freshly precipitated samples A, B, and C of hydrous oxide ZrO_2 (0.05 gm ZrO_2) at 35°, it has been observed that the order of the reaction deviates from first to second on decreasing the concentration of the peroxide.

1. S. Ghosh and co-workers, *Kolloid -Z.*, 1945, **135**, 43; *ibid.*, 1954, **137**, 26; *ibid.*, 1955, **141**, 106; *Zeit. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **31**, 20476.
2. B. P. Gyani and D. R. Nabe, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 717.
3. K. M. Pant and S. P. Mushran, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 737.

This is attributed to a critical ratio $[H_2O_2]/[ZrO_2]$. The departure set in at 0.02N hydrogen peroxide. This observation was confirmed by performing another set of experiments at 35° in which the amount of the catalyst was varied from 0.0238–0.1904 gm while the concentration of hydrogen peroxide was maintained constant at 0.02N. A perusal of the plots of $\log(a/a-x)$ against t (Fig. 1), where the various terms have their usual meanings, explicitly confirms the contention that a certain critical ratio $[H_2O_2]/[ZrO_2]$ is responsible for setting the deviation in the course of the reaction. On studying the decomposition at different temperatures (30°, 40° and 50°) it has been observed that the reaction is associated with fairly low values of the energy of activation (8.4 Kcals./mole), the latter being independent of the concentration of the peroxide. The experimental data leads to the conclusion that for concentrated solutions of hydrogen peroxide the catalytic activity of the various samples follows the order $A = C > B$ whereas for dilute solutions of the peroxide $A > C > B$. This is attributed to the difference in the particle size of these suspensions.

It appears that hydrogen peroxide forms an adsorption complex $[X]OH-OH$, where $[X]$ denotes the catalyst surface, with hydrous oxide ZrO_2 which eventually breaks up resulting in the formation of free radicals OH . These free radicals OH initiate a chain of reactions^{4,5} as follows :—

The kinetic observations made during the course of present investigation can be explained on the basis of the rate law (derived on the basis of Freundlich Adsorption Isotherm),

$$-\frac{dx}{dt} = k'_1[H_2O_2]^{1/n}[H_2O_2], \quad \dots (iii)$$

where n is the constant of the Freundlich Equation, preceded by the initial step

$$-\frac{dx}{dt} = k_1[H_2O_2] [OH],$$

4. J. Weiss, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, **31**, 1547; *Naturwiss.*, 1935, **23**, 64.

5. H. C. Urey, L. H. Dawsey and F. O. Rice, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 1371.

according to which the decomposition would be a first order process for concentrated solutions of hydrogen peroxide and a second order process for dilute solutions of the peroxide because in the former case the rate of formation of free radicals OH is not dependent upon the concentration of hydrogen peroxide whereas in the latter case the same is dependent on the concentration of the peroxide.

The rapid loss of hydrogen peroxide at the beginning of the reaction, as is evident from a perusal of Fig. 1, is attributed to the formation of an unstable true peroxy compound, viz., $Zr(OH)_3 \cdot O \cdot OH$ (highly active), which eventually changes into a stable true peroxy compound $ZrO_3 \cdot 2H_2O$ (less active) responsible for slowing down the rate of decomposition after some time. This stable compound was isolated from the reaction-products and was found to liberate iodine from a solution of potassium iodide; a property similar to that of potassium peroxydisulphate, a true peroxy compound.

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